

Appendix A for “Do Parents’ Socioeconomic Resources Moderate the Association between Genotype and Cognitive Skills among Children with Diverse Genetic Ancestries?”

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The Construction of Ancestry Groups

European analytic sample (n=475): The European analytic sample includes all participants who had PC loadings of $PC1 > 0.018$ and $PC2 > -0.0075$ from the global PC analysis of *all* unrelated study subjects, since this area is consistent with 1000G EUR super population clusters. For this reason, this group may contain individuals who self-identify as a race/ethnicity other than “White”.

African analytic sample – less admixed (n=1528): The less admixed African analytic sample includes all participants who had PC loadings of $P1 < -0.005$ and $PC2 > 0.007+0.75(PC1)$ from the global PC analysis of *all* unrelated study subjects, since this area is consistent with 1000G AFR super population clusters. The FFCWS team flagged this group in the data for those wishing to do analyses or sensitivity analyses on a more genetically clustered group. **NB:** this group may contain individuals who self-identify as a race/ethnicity other than “Non-Hispanic Black”. The FFCWS Genetics team defined a more **Admixed African analytic sample (n=1640)** for those wishing to do analyses with a more admixed sample of African ancestry. This is the sample we use.

Hispanic analytic sample – less admixed (n=640): The less admixed Hispanic analytic sample includes all participants who had PC loadings of $PC1 > 0.018$ and $-0.055 < PC2 < 0.025$ from the global PC analysis of *all* unrelated study subjects. Because Hispanic genetic ancestry is incredibly diverse, this area is consistent with only some of the 1000G AMR super population clusters (specifically CLM-Medellin, Colombia, PEL-Lima, Peru). **NB:** this group may contain individuals who self-identify as a race/ethnicity other than “Hispanic”. The FFCWS Genetics Team flagged this group in the data for those wishing to do analyses or sensitivity analyses on a more genetically clustered group. The FFCWS also flagged a more **Admixed Hispanic analytic sample (n=959)** in the data for those wishing to do analyses or sensitivity analyses on a more admixed sample of Hispanic ancestry. This is the sample we use.

Local “within-analytic-group” genetic principal components: Once the FFCWS Genetics Team had identified the analytic samples (European, n=475; Admixed African, n=1640; Admixed Hispanic, n=959), they ran principal component analysis within each sample to create sample eigenvectors for covariates in the statistical model used for association testing to adjust for possible population stratification, within-analytic group.

Table A1 Minimum Effect Size of the Interaction Terms to Achieve a Statistical Power > 80%,
Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study

	Corr(PGI,Y)	Corr(Moderator, Y)	Corr(PGI, Moderator)	Min. effect size
African ancestries				
<i>Maternal education as moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.096	0.332	0.110	0.065
WISC	0.085	0.107	0.110	0.075
<i>Log household Income as the moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.096	0.310	0.073	0.070
WISC	0.085	0.111	0.073	0.075
Hispanic ancestries				
<i>Maternal education as moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.160	0.499	0.158	0.085
WISC	0.073	0.259	0.262	0.090
<i>Log household Income as the moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.160	0.422	0.132	0.085
WISC	0.073	0.223	0.132	0.095
European ancestries				
<i>Maternal education as moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.221	0.345	0.365	0.130
WISC	0.096	0.245	0.245	0.130
<i>Log household Income as the moderator</i>				
PPVT	0.221	0.271	0.268	0.130
WISC	0.096	0.184	0.268	0.135

Note: Calculation of the minimum effect size to achieve a statistical power of 80% was carried out using the Shiny App (<https://mfinsaas.shinyapps.io/InteractionPowerR/>) (Baranger et al. 2023). For each sample and each moderator (maternal education and household income per household member) we provide minimum effect sizes for the outcome most correlated with the EA PGI (PPVT) and minimum effect sizes for the outcome least correlated with the EA PGI (WISC). Effect sizes are measured in standard deviations. PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index.

Table A2 Effect Size of EA PGI x SES on Cognitive Skills in Previous Studies

Reference	Ancestry	Country	Data	Mean age	Sample size	Effect size	S.E.
Peñaherrera-Aguirre et al. 2022	Mixed	US	ABCD	9.5	7,880	0.020	0.010
Selzam et al. 2017	European	UK	TEDS	7	3,848	-0.010	0.015
Houmark et al. 2024	European	DK	iPSYCH	8	16,040	0.015	0.008
Houmark et al. 2024	European	DK	iPSYCH	10	21,390	0.003	0.007

Note: We report effect sizes for studies with a comparable age range to the children in our sample (9 years old). SES is operationalized differently in each study. Peñaherrera-Aguirre et al. 2022 measure SES as financial adversity in different contexts (reversed), neighborhood safety, parental marital status, parental educational attainment, parents' employment status, family income. Selzam et al. 2017 measure SES as maternal age at birth of eldest child, the mean score of maternal and paternal highest education level, as respondent's (mother or father) occupation, administered by the Standard Occupational Classification 2000 (Office for National Statistics, 2000) at child age 2. Houmark et al. 2024 measure SES as average family income, maternal and paternal years of education, whether the mother and father has ever received a psychiatric diagnosis, and the fraction of time parents have not been divorced. DK: Denmark. UK: United Kingdom. US: The United States. ABCD: Adolescent Brain Cognitive Development, TEDS: The Twins Early Development Study, iPSYCH: The Lundbeck Foundation Initiative for Integrative Psychiatric Research.

Table A3 Sharpened False Discovery Rate Q-Values and Meta-Estimates, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample

	Table	Coef.	s.e.	p-value	q-value
Child's EA PGI					
<i>PPVT</i>	3	0.068	0.024	0.005	0.017
<i>WJPC</i>	3	0.054	0.025	0.028	0.069
<i>WJAP</i>	3	0.052	0.025	0.033	0.07
<i>WISC</i>	3	0.078	0.025	0.002	0.015
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.063		0.0001	
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS					
<i>PPVT</i>	2	0.019	0.054	0.719	0.596
<i>WJPC</i>	2	-0.002	0.054	0.964	0.715
<i>WJAP</i>	2	-0.001	0.054	0.978	0.715
<i>WISC</i>	2	-0.015	0.055	0.784	0.596
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.0003		0.9926	
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member					
<i>PPVT</i>	3	0.02	0.029	0.493	0.413
<i>WJPC</i>	3	0.009	0.029	0.748	0.596
<i>WJAP</i>	3	0.02	0.029	0.496	0.413
<i>WISC</i>	3	0.019	0.03	0.527	0.414
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.017		0.2457	

Note: n=1,551. The sharpened false discovery rate (FDR) q-values are based on Benjamini et al. 2006 and calculated using code by McKenzie 2021. Meta-estimates are calculated as a fixed effect model using the R package meta. PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A4 Sharpened False Discovery Rate Q-Values and Meta-Estimates, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample

	Table	Coef.	s.e.	p-value	q-value
Child's EA PGI					
<i>PPVT</i>	5	0.095	0.029	0.001	0.014
<i>WJPC</i>	5	0.11	0.032	0.001	0.014
<i>WJAP</i>	5	0.096	0.032	0.003	0.016
<i>WISC</i>	5	0.047	0.033	0.148	0.174
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.088		0.0001	
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS					
<i>PPVT</i>	4	0.19	0.066	0.004	0.017
<i>WJPC</i>	4	0.111	0.069	0.108	0.145
<i>WJAP</i>	4	0.104	0.07	0.135	0.171
<i>WISC</i>	4	0.118	0.07	0.094	0.136
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.1328		0.0001	
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member					
<i>PPVT</i>	5	0.078	0.035	0.028	0.069
<i>WJPC</i>	5	0.078	0.038	0.041	0.08
<i>WJAP</i>	5	0	0.039	0.9999	0.715
<i>WISC</i>	5	0.035	0.04	0.379	0.34
<i>meta-estimate</i>		0.0494		0.0089	

Note: n=890. The sharpened false discovery rate (FDR) q-values are based on Benjamini et al. 2006 and calculated using code by McKenzie 2021. Meta-estimates are calculated as a fixed effect model using the R package meta. PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A5 Means and Standard Deviations for the Analytic Samples, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries Sample

	Mean	Std. Dev.
Polygenic index of educational attainment	0	1
PPVT	0	1
WJPC	0	1
WJAP	0	1
WISC	0	1
Mother's education > high school	0.61	0.49
Married parents at birth	0.56	0.50
Household income*	62185.20	49342.40
N		442

Note: *the average of the available variables on mothers' household income at birth, age 3, age 5, and age 9. PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest.

Table A6 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Mother's Education at Birth, Future of Families and Child Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries Sample

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.12*	(0.05)	0.18*	(0.09)	0.09	(0.05)	0.03	(0.09)
Mother's education>HS	0.35**	(0.11)	0.33**	(0.12)	0.49***	(0.11)	0.51***	(0.12)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			-0.09	(0.11)			0.10	(0.10)
Constant	0.07	(0.37)	0.12	(0.38)	-0.26	(0.37)	-0.31	(0.38)
N	442		442		442		442	
R ²	0.16		0.16		0.17		0.17	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.13**	(0.05)	0.13	(0.09)	0.02	(0.05)	-0.07	(0.09)
Mother's education>HS	0.59***	(0.11)	0.60***	(0.12)	0.30*	(0.12)	0.33**	(0.12)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.01	(0.10)			0.14	(0.11)
Constant	-0.47	(0.37)	-0.48	(0.38)	-0.49	(0.39)	-0.57	(0.39)
N	442		442		442		442	
R ²	0.16		0.16		0.09		0.10	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HS: high school.

Table A7 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries Sample

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.12*	(0.05)	0.42	(0.58)	0.09	(0.05)	0.17	(0.58)
Log household income/member	0.19*	(0.08)	0.18*	(0.08)	0.17*	(0.08)	0.17*	(0.08)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			-0.03	(0.06)			-0.01	(0.06)
Mother's education>HS	0.23	(0.12)	0.23	(0.12)	0.38**	(0.12)	0.38**	(0.12)
Constant	-1.65*	(0.82)	-1.57	(0.83)	-1.83*	(0.81)	-1.80*	(0.83)
N	442		442		442		442	
R ²	0.17		0.17		0.18		0.18	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.13**	(0.05)	0.90	(0.58)	0.02	(0.05)	-0.42	(0.61)
Log household income/member	0.07	(0.08)	0.06	(0.08)	0.10	(0.08)	0.11	(0.08)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			-0.08	(0.06)			0.05	(0.06)
Mother's education>HS	0.55***	(0.12)	0.54***	(0.12)	0.24	(0.13)	0.24	(0.13)
Constant	-1.15	(0.82)	-0.95	(0.83)	-1.44	(0.85)	-1.56	(0.87)
N	442		442		442		442	
R ²	0.17		0.17		0.10		0.10	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Figure A1 Associations between Child’s Educational Attainment Polygenic Index and Cognitive Skills by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries Sample

Note: N=442. HS=high school or less, >HS=more education than high school. All models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05; †p<0.1; ns=not significant (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest

Figure A2 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries
 Broad ancestry definition (n=1,551) Narrow ancestry definition (n=1,449)

	Mean	Variance	N		Mean	Variance	N
HS or less	-0.054	0.999	1082	HS or less	-0.053	1.002	1016
More th. HS	0.128	0.982	469	More th. HS	0.129	0.974	433

Note: HS stands for high school.

Figure A3 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries
 Broad ancestry definition (n=890) Narrow ancestry definition (n=604)

	Mean	Variance	N		Mean	Variance	N
HS or less	-0.073	0.952	627	HS or less	-0.044	0.957	434
More th. HS	0.17	1.077	263	More th. HS	0.104	1.094	170

Note: HS stands for high school.

Figure A4 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries (n=442)

	Mean	Variance	N
HS or less	-0.391	0.755	173
More th. HS	0.251	0.999	269

Note: HS stands for high school.

Figure A5 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Quintiles of Maternal Household Income per Person, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries

Broad ancestry definition (n=1,551)

Narrow ancestry definition (n=1,449)

	Mean	Variance	N		Mean	Variance	N
1st	-0.024	0.966	383	1st	-0.013	0.97	373
2nd	-0.079	1.066	358	2nd	-0.07	1.059	335
3rd	0.008	0.945	342	3rd	-0.001	0.97	316
4th	0.016	0.964	303	4th	0.011	0.956	271
5th	0.192	1.09	165	5th	0.177	1.069	154

Figure A6 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Quintiles of Maternal Household Income per Person, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries
 Broad ancestry definition (n=890) Narrow ancestry definition (n=604)

	Mean	Variance	N		Mean	Variance	N
1st	-0.16	0.867	160	1st	-0.121	0.887	118
2nd	-0.098	1.015	204	2nd	-0.123	1.073	146
3rd	-0.016	0.972	201	3rd	-0.025	0.903	131
4th	0.073	0.912	183	4th	0.095	0.917	118
5th	0.242	1.203	142	5th	0.251	1.189	91

Figure A7 Density Plot of Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Quintiles of Maternal Household Income per Person, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries (n=442)

	Mean	Variance	N
1st	-0.778	0.349	14
2nd	-0.408	0.817	35
3rd	-0.312	0.944	61
4th	-0.07	0.848	106
5th	0.229	1.024	226

Table A8 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Mother's Education at Birth, Future of Families and Child Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, *Narrowly Defined Ancestry*

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.07**	(0.03)	0.06*	(0.03)	0.06*	(0.03)	0.06	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.52***	(0.06)	0.52***	(0.06)	0.35***	(0.06)	0.35***	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.04	(0.06)			0.01	(0.06)
Constant	-0.05	(0.11)	-0.05	(0.11)	-0.43***	(0.11)	-0.43***	(0.11)
N	1,449		1,449		1,449		1,449	
R ²	0.10		0.10		0.08		0.08	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.06*	(0.03)	0.06	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08*	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.39***	(0.06)	0.39***	(0.06)	0.13*	(0.06)	0.13*	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.00	(0.06)			0.00	(0.06)
Constant	-0.31**	(0.11)	-0.31**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)
N	1,449		1,449		1,449		1,449	
R ²	0.08		0.08		0.05		0.05	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGS is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HS: high school.

Table A9 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, *Narrowly Defined Ancestry*

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGS	0.07**	(0.02)	0.07**	(0.02)	0.06*	(0.03)	0.06*	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.32***	(0.04)	0.32***	(0.04)	0.23***	(0.04)	0.23***	(0.04)
Child's EA PGS x log HH income/member			0.02	(0.03)			0.01	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.29***	(0.06)	0.29***	(0.06)	0.19**	(0.06)	0.19**	(0.06)
Constant	0.07	(0.11)	0.06	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)
N	1,449		1,449		1,449		1,449	
R ²	0.15		0.15		0.11		0.11	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGS	0.05*	(0.03)	0.05*	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.21***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.10*	(0.04)	0.10**	(0.04)
Child's EA PGS x log HH income/member			0.03	(0.03)			0.02	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.23***	(0.06)	0.23***	(0.06)	0.06	(0.06)	0.06	(0.06)
Constant	-0.24*	(0.11)	-0.24*	(0.11)	-0.31**	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)
N	1,449		1,449		1,449		1,449	
R ²	0.10		0.10		0.06		0.06	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A10a Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Mother's Education at Birth, Future of Families and Child Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, Removal of Influential Cases

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.07**	(0.02)	0.07*	(0.03)	0.06*	(0.02)	0.06	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.52***	(0.05)	0.52***	(0.06)	0.35***	(0.06)	0.35***	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.01	(0.05)			-0.00	(0.05)
Constant	-0.09	(0.11)	-0.09	(0.11)	-0.46***	(0.11)	-0.46***	(0.11)
N	1,529		1,529		1,529		1,529	
R ²	0.09		0.09		0.08		0.08	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.06*	(0.02)	0.06*	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.39***	(0.06)	0.39***	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			-0.00	(0.05)			-0.01	(0.06)
Constant	-0.35**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)	-0.35**	(0.11)
N	1,529		1,529		1,529		1,529	
R ²	0.09		0.09		0.05		0.05	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with nine principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HS: high school.

Table A10b Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, Removal of Influential Cases

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.07**	(0.02)	0.07**	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)
Log household income/member	0.33***	(0.03)	0.33***	(0.03)	0.21***	(0.04)	0.21***	(0.04)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			0.02	(0.03)			0.02	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.28***	(0.06)	0.28***	(0.06)	0.21***	(0.06)	0.20***	(0.06)
Constant	0.04	(0.10)	0.04	(0.10)	-0.38***	(0.11)	-0.38***	(0.11)
N	1,535		1,535		1,535		1,535	
R ²	0.14		0.14		0.10		0.10	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.06*	(0.02)	0.06*	(0.02)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.21***	(0.04)	0.21***	(0.04)	0.08*	(0.04)	0.08*	(0.04)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			0.02	(0.03)			0.02	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.25***	(0.06)	0.25***	(0.06)	0.09	(0.06)	0.09	(0.06)
Constant	-0.27*	(0.11)	-0.28*	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)
N	1,535		1,535		1,535		1,535	
R ²	0.11		0.11		0.06		0.06	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with nine principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A11 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education Controlled for Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.07**	(0.02)	0.06*	(0.03)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.06	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.28***	(0.06)	0.28***	(0.06)	0.20**	(0.06)	0.20**	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.02	(0.05)			-0.01	(0.05)
Log household income/member	0.33***	(0.03)	0.33***	(0.03)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)
Constant	-2.79***	(0.30)	-2.79***	(0.30)	-2.27***	(0.31)	-2.27***	(0.31)
N	1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551	
R ²	0.14		0.14		0.10		0.10	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.05*	(0.02)	0.05	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)
Mother's education>HS	0.24***	(0.06)	0.24***	(0.06)	0.09	(0.06)	0.09	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			-0.00	(0.05)			-0.02	(0.06)
Log household income/member	0.21***	(0.04)	0.21***	(0.04)	0.09*	(0.04)	0.09*	(0.04)
Constant	-2.09***	(0.31)	-2.09***	(0.31)	-1.04***	(0.31)	-1.04***	(0.31)
N	1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551	
R ²	0.10		0.10		0.06		0.06	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with nine principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A12 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Mother's Education at Birth, Future of Families and Child Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, *Narrowly Defined Ancestry*

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.14***	(0.04)	0.07	(0.05)	0.16***	(0.04)	0.11*	(0.05)
Mother's education>HS	0.71***	(0.09)	0.70***	(0.09)	0.48***	(0.09)	0.47***	(0.09)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.25**	(0.08)			0.17*	(0.08)
Constant	-0.73***	(0.12)	-0.73***	(0.12)	-0.47***	(0.13)	-0.47***	(0.13)
N	604		604		604		604	
R ²	0.20		0.21		0.14		0.14	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.17***	(0.04)	0.12*	(0.05)	0.07	(0.04)	0.03	(0.05)
Mother's education>HS	0.44***	(0.09)	0.43***	(0.09)	0.35***	(0.09)	0.34***	(0.09)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.16	(0.09)			0.13	(0.09)
Constant	-0.18	(0.13)	-0.18	(0.13)	-0.40**	(0.13)	-0.41**	(0.13)
N	604		604		604		604	
R ²	0.10		0.11		0.10		0.10	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HS: high school.

Table A13 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, *Narrowly Defined Ancestry*

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.11**	(0.04)	0.11**	(0.04)	0.14***	(0.04)	0.14***	(0.04)
Log household income/member	0.43***	(0.05)	0.42***	(0.05)	0.27***	(0.06)	0.26***	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			0.08	(0.04)			0.13**	(0.05)
Mother's education>HS	0.40***	(0.09)	0.41***	(0.09)	0.29**	(0.10)	0.30**	(0.10)
Constant	-0.55***	(0.12)	-0.56***	(0.12)	-0.36**	(0.13)	-0.37**	(0.13)
N	604		604		604		604	
R ²	0.28		0.29		0.17		0.18	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.15***	(0.04)	0.15***	(0.04)	0.06	(0.04)	0.06	(0.04)
Log household income/member	0.29***	(0.06)	0.29***	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			-0.01	(0.05)			0.04	(0.05)
Mother's education>HS	0.23*	(0.10)	0.23*	(0.10)	0.25*	(0.10)	0.25*	(0.10)
Constant	-0.06	(0.13)	-0.06	(0.13)	-0.35**	(0.13)	-0.35**	(0.13)
N	604		604		604		604	
R ²	0.14		0.14		0.11		0.11	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A14 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education Controlled for Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.09**	(0.03)	0.03	(0.04)	0.11***	(0.03)	0.07	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.44***	(0.07)	0.42***	(0.07)	0.28***	(0.08)	0.27***	(0.08)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.19**	(0.06)			0.11	(0.07)
Log household income/member	0.44***	(0.04)	0.44***	(0.04)	0.31***	(0.05)	0.31***	(0.05)
Constant	-4.28***	(0.37)	-4.30***	(0.36)	-2.96***	(0.40)	-2.97***	(0.40)
N	890		890		890		890	
R ²	0.29		0.30		0.17		0.17	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.10**	(0.03)	0.06	(0.04)	0.05	(0.03)	0.01	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.25**	(0.08)	0.24**	(0.08)	0.25**	(0.08)	0.23**	(0.08)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.11	(0.07)			0.12	(0.07)
Log household income/member	0.32***	(0.05)	0.32***	(0.05)	0.19***	(0.05)	0.19***	(0.05)
Constant	-2.87***	(0.40)	-2.88***	(0.40)	-1.86***	(0.41)	-1.87***	(0.41)
N	890		890		890		890	
R ²	0.15		0.16		0.11		0.11	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with ten principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody picture vocabulary test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A15 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Mother's Education at Birth, Future of Families and Child Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, Removal of Influential Cases

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.12***	(0.03)	0.05	(0.04)	0.13***	(0.03)	0.08*	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.76***	(0.07)	0.74***	(0.07)	0.51***	(0.07)	0.49***	(0.07)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.23***	(0.07)			0.17*	(0.07)
Constant	-0.66***	(0.10)	-0.67***	(0.10)	-0.45***	(0.11)	-0.46***	(0.11)
N	873		873		873		873	
R ²	0.20		0.22		0.13		0.14	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA PGI	0.12***	(0.03)	0.07	(0.04)	0.06	(0.03)	0.01	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.49***	(0.07)	0.47***	(0.07)	0.39***	(0.08)	0.37***	(0.08)
Child's EA PGI x mother's education>HS			0.16*	(0.07)			0.17*	(0.07)
Constant	-0.23*	(0.11)	-0.23*	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)
N	873		873		873		873	
R ²	0.11		0.11		0.10		0.10	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA PGI is residualized with ten principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HS: high school.

Table A16 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, Removal of Influential Cases

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.09**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.11***	(0.03)	0.10***	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.43***	(0.04)	0.43***	(0.04)	0.30***	(0.05)	0.29***	(0.05)
Child's EA-PGI x log HH income/member			0.10**	(0.04)			0.11**	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.45***	(0.07)	0.45***	(0.07)	0.30***	(0.08)	0.30***	(0.08)
Constant	-0.45***	(0.10)	-0.46***	(0.10)	-0.30**	(0.11)	-0.31**	(0.11)
N	874		874		874		874	
R ²	0.30		0.30		0.17		0.18	
	WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.10**	(0.03)	0.10**	(0.03)	0.05	(0.03)	0.04	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.32***	(0.05)	0.32***	(0.05)	0.20***	(0.05)	0.20***	(0.05)
Child's EA-PGI x log HH income/member			0.03	(0.04)			0.07	(0.04)
Mother's education>HS	0.26**	(0.08)	0.26**	(0.08)	0.25**	(0.08)	0.25**	(0.08)
Constant	-0.07	(0.11)	-0.07	(0.11)	-0.22*	(0.11)	-0.23*	(0.11)
N	874		874		874		874	
R ²	0.15		0.15		0.12		0.12	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with ten principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody picture vocabulary test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household, HS: high school.

Table A17 Comparison of Respondents across Available Data, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study

	Test score at age 9?		Genotyped?		In the analytic sample?	
	no	yes	no	yes	no	yes
Maternal education at birth						
< high school	38% (603)	33% (1096)	37% (674)	33% (1025)	36% (726)	34% (973)
High school	27% (440)	32% (1040)	28% (511)	32% (969)	28% (571)	32% (909)
Some college	23% (372)	25% (817)	23% (424)	25% (765)	24% (475)	25% (714)
College+	12% (190)	10% (334)	12% (213)	10% (311)	12% (237)	10% (287)
χ^2 p-value	0.001		0.005		0.018	
Quintiles of mother's average household income per person age 0-9						
1 st	21% (343)	19% (637)	21% (391)	19% (589)	21% (423)	19% (557)
2 nd	19% (301)	21% (678)	19% (340)	21% (639)	19% (382)	21% (597)
3 rd	18% (282)	21% (697)	19% (343)	21% (636)	19% (375)	21% (604)
4 th	20% (317)	20% (662)	19% (345)	21% (634)	19% (387)	21% (592)
5 th	23% (362)	19% (617)	22% (403)	19% (576)	22% (446)	18% (533)
χ^2 p-value	0.001		0.003		0.004	
Mother's average household income per person age 0-9						
mean	9518	8659	9339	8704	9348	8656
t-test p-value	0.006		0.031		0.016	
N	1,605	3,287	1,822	3,070	2,009	2,883

Note: The availability of test score data at age 9 is defined as having a valid response to the Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, and Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest.

Table A18 Means and Standard Deviation for Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study

	African Ancestries		Latinx Ancestries		European Ancestries	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Less than high school	0.34	0.47	0.44	0.50	0.14	0.35
High school	0.36	0.48	0.27	0.44	0.25	0.43
Some college	0.26	0.44	0.22	0.42	0.26	0.44
College	0.04	0.21	0.07	0.26	0.35	0.48
N	1,551		890		442	

Table A19 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, Broadly defined ancestry

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC		WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.07**	(0.02)	0.02	(0.04)	0.06*	(0.02)	0.01	(0.04)	0.06*	(0.02)	-0.01	(0.04)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.04	(0.04)
Mother's education, ref.: less than high school																
<i>High school</i>	0.12*	(0.06)	0.12*	(0.06)	0.07	(0.06)	0.08	(0.06)	0.03	(0.06)	0.04	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)	0.14*	(0.06)
<i>Some college</i>	0.55***	(0.07)	0.55***	(0.07)	0.37***	(0.07)	0.37***	(0.07)	0.38***	(0.07)	0.38***	(0.07)	0.21**	(0.07)	0.21**	(0.07)
<i>College</i>	0.83***	(0.13)	0.83***	(0.13)	0.57***	(0.13)	0.58***	(0.14)	0.63***	(0.13)	0.67***	(0.13)	0.31*	(0.13)	0.35*	(0.14)
Child's EA-PGI x Mother's education																
<i>High school</i>			0.10	(0.06)			0.09	(0.06)			0.13*	(0.06)			0.08	(0.06)
<i>Some college</i>			0.06	(0.06)			0.04	(0.06)			0.08	(0.06)			0.04	(0.07)
<i>College</i>			0.07	(0.12)			0.02	(0.13)			-0.06	(0.13)			-0.06	(0.13)
Constant	-0.14	(0.11)	-0.15	(0.11)	-0.49***	(0.11)	-0.50***	(0.11)	-0.36**	(0.11)	-0.38***	(0.11)	-0.42***	(0.11)	-0.43***	(0.11)
N	1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551	
R2	0.10		0.10		0.08		0.08		0.08		0.09		0.06		0.06	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with nine principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index.

Table A20 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, Broadly defined ancestry

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC		WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.10***	(0.03)	0.01	(0.05)	0.11***	(0.03)	-0.00	(0.05)	0.10**	(0.03)	0.05	(0.05)	0.05	(0.03)	-0.01	(0.05)
Mother's education, ref.: less than high school																
<i>High school</i>	0.33***	(0.07)	0.34***	(0.07)	0.24**	(0.08)	0.25**	(0.08)	0.21**	(0.08)	0.22**	(0.08)	0.12	(0.08)	0.13	(0.08)
<i>Some college</i>	0.75***	(0.08)	0.75***	(0.08)	0.47***	(0.08)	0.48***	(0.08)	0.47***	(0.09)	0.47***	(0.09)	0.32***	(0.09)	0.31***	(0.09)
<i>College</i>	1.55***	(0.13)	1.50***	(0.14)	1.16***	(0.14)	1.17***	(0.15)	1.03***	(0.14)	1.03***	(0.15)	0.91***	(0.14)	0.94***	(0.15)
Child's EA-PGI x Mother's education																
<i>High school</i>			0.09	(0.07)			0.23**	(0.08)			0.05	(0.08)			0.07	(0.08)
<i>Some college</i>			0.20*	(0.08)			0.19*	(0.08)			0.12	(0.08)			0.16	(0.08)
<i>College</i>			0.21	(0.12)			0.11	(0.13)			0.04	(0.13)			-0.01	(0.13)
Constant	-0.70***	(0.10)	-0.71***	(0.10)	-0.46***	(0.11)	-0.47***	(0.11)	-0.24*	(0.11)	-0.25*	(0.11)	-0.31**	(0.11)	-0.32**	(0.11)
N	890		890		890		890		890		890		890		890	
R2	0.25		0.26		0.16		0.17		0.13		0.13		0.11		0.11	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with ten principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody picture vocabulary test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index.

Table A21 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Maternal Education, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, European Ancestries Sample

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC		WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.11*	(0.05)	0.36*	(0.14)	0.09	(0.05)	0.22	(0.14)	0.13**	(0.05)	0.27	(0.14)	0.01	(0.05)	0.13	(0.14)
Mother's education, ref.: less than high school																
<i>High school</i>	0.39*	(0.15)	0.22	(0.17)	0.26	(0.15)	0.13	(0.17)	0.29	(0.15)	0.17	(0.17)	0.05	(0.16)	-0.07	(0.18)
<i>Some college</i>	0.54***	(0.16)	0.40*	(0.18)	0.55***	(0.16)	0.47**	(0.17)	0.73***	(0.16)	0.65***	(0.18)	0.15	(0.16)	0.08	(0.18)
<i>College</i>	0.69***	(0.17)	0.53**	(0.19)	0.81***	(0.17)	0.72***	(0.18)	0.86***	(0.17)	0.77***	(0.19)	0.63***	(0.18)	0.54**	(0.19)
Child's EA-PGI x Mother's education																
<i>High school</i>			-0.33	(0.17)			-0.33	(0.17)			-0.27	(0.17)			-0.30	(0.18)
<i>Some college</i>			-0.32	(0.17)			-0.11	(0.16)			-0.12	(0.17)			-0.11	(0.17)
<i>College</i>			-0.23	(0.16)			-0.09	(0.16)			-0.15	(0.16)			-0.06	(0.17)
Constant	-0.19	(0.38)	-0.07	(0.40)	-0.46	(0.38)	-0.43	(0.39)	-0.67	(0.38)	-0.60	(0.40)	-0.61	(0.39)	-0.60	(0.41)
N	442		442		442		442		442		442		442		442	
R2	0.17		0.18		0.19		0.20		0.17		0.18		0.12		0.13	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with five principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index.

Table A22 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, African Ancestries Sample, Broadly defined ancestry

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC		WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.	coef.	s.e.
Child's EA-PGI	0.07**	(0.02)	0.07**	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.05*	(0.02)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.33***	(0.04)	0.33***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.22***	(0.04)	0.07	(0.04)	0.07	(0.04)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			0.02	(0.03)			0.01	(0.03)			0.02	(0.03)			0.02	(0.03)
Mother's education, ref.: high school																
< high school	0.01	(0.06)	0.01	(0.06)	0.01	(0.06)	0.01	(0.06)	(0.06)	0.05	(0.06)	-0.11	(0.06)	-0.11	(0.06)	(0.06)
Some college	0.28***	(0.06)	0.28***	(0.06)	0.20**	(0.07)	0.20**	(0.07)	(0.07)	0.25***	(0.07)	0.04	(0.07)	0.04	(0.07)	(0.07)
College	0.36**	(0.13)	0.35**	(0.13)	0.26	(0.13)	0.26	(0.13)	(0.13)	0.36**	(0.13)	0.11	(0.14)	0.10	(0.14)	(0.13)
Constant	-0.14	(0.11)	-0.15	(0.11)	-0.49***	(0.11)	-0.50***	(0.11)	-0.36**	(0.11)	-0.38***	(0.11)	-0.42***	(0.11)	-0.43***	(0.11)
N	1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551		1,551	
R ²	0.14		0.14		0.10		0.10		0.10		0.10		0.06		0.06	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with nine principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household.

Table A23 Interaction Results from Child's Educational Attainment Polygenic Index by Household Income per Household Member, Future of Families Child and Wellbeing Study, Latinx Ancestries Sample, Broadly defined ancestry

	PPVT		PPVT		WJPC		WJPC		WJAP		WJAP		WISC		WISC	
	coef.	s.e.														
Child's EA-PGI	0.09**	(0.03)	0.08**	(0.03)	0.10**	(0.03)	0.10**	(0.03)	0.09**	(0.03)	0.09**	(0.03)	0.04	(0.03)	0.04	(0.03)
Log household income/member	0.38***	(0.05)	0.38***	(0.05)	0.25***	(0.05)	0.25***	(0.05)	0.28***	(0.05)	0.28***	(0.05)	0.15**	(0.05)	0.15**	(0.05)
Child's EA PGI x log HH income/member			0.06	(0.04)			0.06	(0.04)			-0.02	(0.04)			0.01	(0.04)
Mother's education, ref.: high school																
< high school	-0.16*	(0.07)	-0.16*	(0.07)	-0.12	(0.08)	-0.12	(0.08)	-0.08	(0.08)	-0.08	(0.08)	-0.05	(0.08)	-0.05	(0.08)
Some college	0.28***	(0.08)	0.29***	(0.08)	0.15	(0.09)	0.15	(0.09)	0.16	(0.09)	0.16	(0.09)	0.15	(0.10)	0.15	(0.10)
College	0.84***	(0.14)	0.81***	(0.14)	0.68***	(0.15)	0.64***	(0.15)	0.54***	(0.15)	0.55***	(0.15)	0.64***	(0.16)	0.64***	(0.16)
Constant	-0.34**	(0.11)	-0.34**	(0.11)	-0.21	(0.12)	-0.21	(0.12)	-0.01	(0.12)	-0.01	(0.12)	-0.18	(0.13)	-0.18	(0.13)
N	890		890		890		890		890		890		890		890	
R ²	0.31		0.31		0.18		0.18		0.16		0.16		0.12		0.12	

Note: all models are controlled for city and marital status at birth. The EA-PGI is residualized with ten principal components and standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. The test scores are standardized to mean zero and standard deviation 1. ***p<0.001; **p<0.01; *p<0.05 (two-tailed). PPVT: Peabody Picture Vocabulary Test, WJPC: Woodcock-Johnson Passage Comprehension test, WJAP: Woodcock-Johnson Applied Problems test, WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children, Digit Span subtest, EA-PGI: educational attainment polygenic index, HH: household.